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Kadirova Marg'uba Buriyevna and Nosirova Arofat Erkinovna**TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR AS A LANGUAGE MATERIAL****Annotation:**

This article revealed in the complex approach to teaching foreign languages paying attention to its main language skills (grammar, vocabulary, listening, speaking, etc.): both theoretical and practical analysis of the classroom activities and completely new methods of teaching foreign languages. Each of the activities is described in details with presenting the goals and results of using them.

Keywords: grammar, phenomenon, reproductive and receptive speech, polysemantics, distribution, translingual and intralingual comparison

Annotatsiya:

Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'qitishga kompleks yondashuvda uning asosiy til ko'nikmalariga (grammatika, lug'at, tinglash, gapirish va h.k.) e'tibor qaratildi: sinf faoliyatining nazariy va amaliy tahlili va chet tillarini o'qitishning mutlaqo yangi usullari. Har bir faoliyat maqsadlari va ulardan foydalanish natijalarini taqdim etgan holda batafsil tavsiflanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: grammatika, hodisa, reproduktiv va retseptiv nutq, polisemantika, tarqatish, translingual va intralingual taqqoslash

Аннотация:

В данной статье раскрывается комплексный подход к обучению иностранному языку с уделением внимания его основным языковым навыкам (грамматике, лексике, аудированию, говорению и др.): как теоретическому, так и практическому анализу учебной деятельности, а также совершенно новым методам обучения иностранным языкам. Каждое из мероприятий подробно описано с указанием целей и результатов их использования.

Ключевые слова: грамматика, феноменон, репродуктивно-рецептивная речь, полисемантика, дистрибуция, межъязыковое и внутриязыковое сопоставление

There are a number of reasons why there occur different concepts about “grammar” when one comes across this term. While it is perceived as a part of Linguistics in the course of mother tongue at the secondary school, in teaching\learning foreign language it is considered to be the grammatical side of the speech. According to various scientific sources the word “grammar” could be limited in two notions:

1) the grammatical side of the speech- structural organization of ideas in speaking, listening, reading and writing (e.g., using articles; speech patterns; verb forms of the person adequately to the context)

2) grammar phenomenon and abstractions (e.g., the first place of the subject in the sentence; the plural form of the noun).

There is a wealth of literature on methodology where one can see such terms as acquiring “grammar mechanisms” as developing grammar sub skills and others. The term “mechanism” is used to describe the events in action. It is more decent to use in short “grammar mechanisms” (V.S.Setlin) than “using grammar elements in speech activity”.

V.S.Setlin has divided the process of acquisition of the grammar mechanisms into three parts:

- 1) acquiring grammar actions
- 2) studying\ learning the suggested material
- 3) mastering grammar generalizations

Grammar actions have the leading position in the grammar mechanisms of speech. Assimilation of grammar actions is classified by the formation of automatized subskills of speech grammar. Learning the suggested material of grammar is defined by memorizing grammar forms. Memorizing and using notions and rules are called as generalization mastering.

The study of the suggested material is called learning grammar units of the foreign language, mastering grammar actions, i.e. developing subskills. Linking (auxiliary) words

and grammar morphemes are learned as a material whilst changing words, word combinations and adhering word order are acquired as subskill.

The notion of grammar material is not a form of grammar phenomenon. The term “form” is associated with the structure of a sentence or a word construction in the plan of the content and expression.

Thus teaching English grammar is associated with assimilation of grammar mechanisms.

The active and passive grammar had been the matter of discussion for a long period. I.V.Rakhmanov used the terms active and passive material in association with mastering the reproductive and receptive speech.

The active grammar means grammar phenomena used in reproductive as well as in productive speech. In some sources the active grammar is called as “grammar of speaking”.

The notion of passive grammar, according to the methodological doctrine of L.V.Scherba, consists of grammar phenomena and their abstractions used in speech perception (reading, listening). Grammar rules of the English language in our brains should be so automatic and familiar to us as to native speakers that we should know when the rules are being violated.

Selection of the grammar material

Micro-form, micro-meaning and micro-usage are recognized as the unit of grammar selection. The grammar phenomena for the oral speech of learners are selected from the real live speech of foreign native speakers and fictions. The resource of selection active grammar is the spoken literary language. Passive grammar minimum is selected from the written texts for students’ receptive speech development.

Active and passive minima do not differ very much as in vocabulary (active minimum is in the passive input), active minimum is selected for all stages of the secondary schools and passive grammar minimum is selected only for lyceums and colleges – for advanced students.

The formation of grammar minima directly deals with the speech themes and vocabulary minima which impact on the grammar selection.

The methodological criteria in preparing of educational grammar are classified as follow.

Criteria of selecting active grammar minimum:

1. Criterion of prevalence of grammar phenomena in oral and written speech. The most frequent phenomena in people's speech are "picked up" from the all grammar system or material.
2. Criterion of being grammar unit as a sample. It requires the ability to developing grammar subkills through given samples (e.g., building noun, adjective, adverb with the help of suffixes).
3. Criterion of isolation of mono-semantic facts. With the aim to prevent difficulties the most frequent and stylistically appropriate units are selected, but only one of the grammar form to excluding synonyms is selected.

Criteria of selecting passive grammar minimum:

1. Criterion of wide usage in literary written style of speech.
2. Criterion of polysemantics.

The element of action and critea of selecting grammar material are directly linked. Some of them as the main, other as complementary. Types of speech activity need various language material input. The most demanding in them are reading and listening. The grammar input for speaking and writing is relativity less than for reading and listening.

The preparation of the English language grammar material requires successful approaches to the selection, distribution and methodical typology of the content of grammar teaching. That's why the selection should be relevant to the above criteria.

The next task of preparation of language material is the presentation of the selected minimum. The distribution of the grammar minimum requires functional approach (according to the communicative tasks). Grammar is divided into communicative units (sentence), so the speech pattern performs as a unit of distribution.

The speech pattern embodies in itself all sides of speech, i.e. vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation and graphic aspects, as speech pattern is considered to be the unit of learning and distribution. Reproductive way of learning English is based on speech patterns leading

to expected results. The speech pattern means a model of a sentence\ utterance which is recognized as a grammar unit\item.

Grammar was distributed in two ways: with the help of the rules and speech patterns. The third way is “lexical approach” which is used when is used when the grammar phenomenon is presented in isolation: if it is used in the only sentence, it needs to be learned without a rule, it should be learnt as a word (lexical item). According to the current educational requirements the method of grammar distribution means using primarily speech patterns, and necessary grammar rules if it is necessary.

The process of distribution consists of three stages:

- 1) defining the general sequence ;
- 2) distribution among the grades ;
- 3) distribution in a school year.

Each stage has its own methodological criteria.

General distribution is measured according to the criterion of importance of grammar phenomena. For example, in distribution of present indefinite and present continuous tenses of the English language, the first one is considered to be the most important for the speech process. The most important grammar phenomena are distributed at the initial stage of education.

Besides, the importance of distribution of grammar among grades occurs when one takes into account the criterion of correlation of grammar with vocabulary. The vocabulary in this case is of primary significance which in its turn influences the distribution of grammar units.

The third stage is a very complex process of distribution. Here are detected the cases of positive or negative transfer of language experience of students. This instructional measure is a major factor of preventing difficulties, i.e. this criterion is directed to prevent the expected grammar errors in the language acquisition. It is called preventing difficulties appearing in the speech.

The first and second distribution is presented in syllabus. The third one is reflected in the English language course books. The result of analysis of translingual and intralingual

comparison of the selected language material are the basis of the grammar typology determination.

It was emphasized in the typology of vocabulary material, that the grammatical facts for learning are also differentiated. The details of easy\difficult acquisition are looked thoroughly. Identification of difficulties and their typology give the opportunity to create a system of exercises, to work out ways of teaching and assign the time period of assimilating the material. The typology of grammar material can be associated with the typology of difficulties in the process of assimilation.

It is known that identification of the difficulties is a multistage instructional organization: analysis of language errors, comparison of the contacted languages (a foreign and native languages) and contrast of the dissimilar elements. The analysis of the errors, comparing and contrasting are organized according to grammatical meaning, form and usage.

Grammar phenomena are taught for developing grammar subskills with the aim to communicate. The process of developing students' grammar subskills is organized within three stages:

1. Presentation stage, in which we introduce the grammar structure, either inductively or deductively. There are a variety of techniques and resources that can be used during this stage. Selection of them should be made according to teacher strengths, student preferences, and the nature of the grammar phenomenon.

2. Focused practice stage, in which the learner manipulates the structure in question while all other variables are held constantly. The goal of this stage is to allow the learner to gain control of the form without pressure and distraction trying to use the proper form of communication.

3. Communicative practice stage, in which the learner is engaged in communicative activities to practice the structures being learned.

It is necessary to pay attention also to teachers' feedback and error correction which can take place throughout the aforementioned two stages, in particular, on the 2-d stage when correction should be predominantly straightforward and immediate; on the 3-d stage

communication should not be interrupted, but the teacher should take notes of the mistakes and deal with them after communicative exercises.

Moreover grammar facts presented in the speech patterns are introduced orally to learners at the lower and middle stages of education, and in written form at the middle and higher stages. Grammar phenomenon is presented via speech pattern or a rule, or via lexical approach. There are two kinds of rules: rule-instruction and rule-generalization.

The rule- instruction is a mental activity aimed at using or reading\listening comprehension of structures, in psycholinguistics the rule is studied in speech issues, this program is called algorithm. Introducing the rule is the advance guiding base directed to providing speech act. In other words, a rule can be defined as a base of speech practice.

The rule- generalization is a simple theoretical information related to grammar material that was learned in the process of speech acquisition. The rule should be laconic, clear and accurately formulated directed to using or recognizing grammar phenomenon.

The rule and model are methodological notions with the same essence. The usage of the model provides capturing of the structural form in person's mind. Verbal abstraction is expressed by words occurred discursively. The speech patterns play the role of samples for composing sentences. Discursiveness must be limited as much as possible.

The factors and ways of developing grammar skills

As it was mentioned, presentation of grammar material is organized either inductively or deductively. Inductive presentation begins from examples and transfers to abstraction, deductive one presents a rule (or a speech pattern) then practices examples. The rule-generalization appears when there are more than one example. Only one structure can be learned without rule within lexical approach.

Many factors should be taken into account in introducing a structure to students:

- 1.The factor of relation to the nature of grammar phenomenon. Similarity of the form, clarity of the meaning requires using of inductive method.
- 2.The factor of similarity and difference between native and a foreign language structures. Similarity makes to use induction and difference makes to use deduction.
- 3.The factor of acquiring language experience.
- 4.The factor of learning micro-units of new structures via different methods.

The choice of the inductive and deductive methods must be rational and relevant. Doing exercises at the focused and communicative stages promotes developing of grammar subskills. It is necessary to stress that grammar subskill is a complex of operations and actions that provides adequate and automatized usage and memorization of morphologic – syntactic structures of speech. Morphologic subskill with the structure (noun suffixes, verb suffixes, grammar units that came before noun, e.g., articles, prepositions, etc.). Syntactic subskill includes word order, building word combinations. The subskill of using structure is made up by changing words and inserting the words into place.

The development of speech skills of students is organized via skill- getting and skill- using exercises which are characterized by the process of manipulating and using the structures in the different contexts.

There is a strong tendency for grammar or points to occur with one of three aspects of the language such as:

1. social factors related to the social roles of interlocutors, intentions and situations, register of speech and others peculiarities;
2. semantic factors related to “negotiation of meaning”, for example, in expressions of location, time, space, degree, quantity, probability, etc. with focus on morphological, lexical and syntactic contrast;
3. discourse factors related to the topic of continuity, word order, and sequencing of new and old information, which effect the forms that propositions take in the context of discourse.

All of the these factors interact with each other, as well as with the structure of the language.

The grammar instructions should take into account these factors in the educational process. Each factor dictates using of some of the techniques for successful communication:

- 1) social- dynamic interactional techniques (e.g. dramatization);
- 2) semantic – listening and responding; demonstration; illustration; static techniques;
- 3) discourse – text generation and manipulation; explanation.

Principles of teaching grammar

Grammar language material is according to the given instructional principles:

I. The principle of developing grammar mechanisms. Teaching structure is associated with the developing of the grammar mechanisms. The grammar mechanism consists of three mentioned parts, as subskills, material and generalization.

Grammar subskills have a special place among the automatized components of speech activity in acquisition of grammar mechanisms. Grammar subskills are developed as reproductive and receptive skills of oral \ written speech.

Grammar skills are composed of generalizations appropriate to rules, i.e. they contain grammar abstractions.

The methods of developing grammar subskills of English are connected with peculiarities of speech activity and difficulties of interrelations of grammar structures of the native language and second language \ foreign language.

Teaching grammar mechanisms of speech must be fulfilled by taking into account the mother tongue of students from the one side and second by overcoming negative influence of mother tongue to the English language speech process: a) the rule can be explained in the mother tongue, whereas the meaning of the structures and their usage should be expressed in English; b) the development of reproductive skills are achieved by regulation of grammar actions and cognitive operations, code switching and appropriate structure selection, all these in combination allow avoiding negative influence of the mother tongue. All these facts must be reflected in exercises and instructions (rules).

Secondly, the content of the teaching grammar mechanisms of speech in English involves the study of linking (auxiliary) words and inflexions. Its acquisition requires creating exact and steady images in students' minds. It is achieved along with acquisition of the skills and also by creating an opportunity to memorize the material.

The third content of acquiring grammar mechanisms of speech includes assimilation of generalizations on the base of materials and actions. Generalizations are learned inductively. The process of learning structures consists of two stages: a) learners understand the rules in the process of doing exercises; b) they discover grammar actions and materials of speech as generalizations.

II. The principle of communicative orientation: a) grammar subskills are acquired in the content of speech activities; b) special grammar exercises can be used at the initial stage of the subskills development.

III. The principle of practical learning of grammar. It reveals learning structures that are important and sufficient for oral and written speech.

IV. The structural principle of teaching grammar. The structural approach to teaching grammar is a well-grounded instruction. A new vocabulary unit is presented in the known speech pattern, and the unknown pattern is presented on the base of acquired vocabulary material.

V. The principle of teaching grammar in speech situations. In teaching English it is referred as situational approach (in American methodology role-play).

VI. The principle of conscious acquisition of grammar. Consciousness presupposes a focus on some elements of the learned speech patterns (sentences).

VII. The principle of differentiated teaching grammar based on the assimilation of the active and passive units which are sorted into reproductive and receptive speech. There are different actions and operation for reproduction and reception.

Besides the aforementioned general principles there are also special principles of teaching grammar (worked out by V.S.Setlin).

The system of teaching grammar consists of developing grammar subskills, acquiring grammar material and learning generalization. In its turn it requires doing exercises aimed at developing skills and acquiring the material. In short exercises are means of overcoming difficulties of structures and assimilation of actions and generalizations. There are some samples of exercises aimed at teaching EL grammar:

1. To discover the structure in the perceived text.
2. To differ new structure from the other known structures.
3. Naming the received \ read structures.
4. To analyze the sentence from grammatical point of view.
5. To continue teacher's story using relevant structures.
6. To use the structure uttered by a students or a teacher.

7. To systemize grammar material (e.g., making up sentences in present, past and future tenses).
8. To use freely structures in speech situation.
9. To describe the picture in the present (past, future) tense in English.
10. To make up conversation using the appropriate structures.
11. To use didactic handout for grammar exercises (individual approach).
12. To translate the sentence (paragraph) that contains difficult structure, etc.

Grammar is very difficult to define. One could consider the systematic features of a language or one could consider the study of those language features. One could go further and look at types of grammar, for example, traditional grammar, formal grammar or functional grammar. A simple defini definition of grammar does not exist. Celce- Murcia and Larsen- Freeman (1999) define grammar as serving two purposes, that is, structure and communicative use. Their definition is based on three levels, which all revolve around sentence structure as the basic unit of meaning in English. The three levels are :

- a) the “subsential or morphological level”;
- b) the “sentential or syntactic level”;
- c) the “suprasentential or discourse level”;

Noam Chomsky is generally considered to be the father of modern linguistics, having begun his contributions to this science in the 1950s. Chomsky developed his original theory of generative grammar, which could be described as rules that show the structure and interpretation of sentences which are accepted by native speakers of a language as the features of that language. Eventually, Chomsky revised this theory and came to a set of universally shared language principles which became known as universal grammar. By the late 1950 he had moved on to syntactic structures from which he developed transformational grammar, which, as a theory, can be described as a method of constructing language by making linguistic transformations including transformations within phrase structures. It can therefore be seen that, in effect, Chomsky began with sentence structure as the basic unit of grammar (generative grammar), but revised his thinking to the smaller unit of phrase structure as the basic grammatical unit (transformational grammar). transformational-

generative grammar research illustrated the fact that learners were capable of creating an infinite number of syntactic combinations.

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